

Arima And ETS Model Performance for Forecasting Nigeria Crude Oil Price

^{1*} Adetunji K. Ilori, ¹ Folakemi M. Okafor, ² Adebisi Michael, ³ Toyosi Adebambo

^{*1}Statistics Programme, National Mathematical Center, Abuja, Nigeria
ilori_adek@yahoo.com

¹Mathematics Programme, National Mathematical Center, Abuja, Nigeria
folayanfe@gmail.com

²Nigeria Centre for Disease Control, Abuja, Nigeria

³Public Health Department, UNICAF University, Zambia.

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the effectiveness of the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) and Exponential Smoothing State Space (ETS) models in forecasting Nigeria's crude oil prices using a time series approach. Monthly crude oil spot prices from January 2009 to May 2024, obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria, served as the dataset. Descriptive analysis revealed significant volatility in oil prices over the study period, with prices ranging from \$14.28 to \$130.10. A time plot and decomposition analysis indicated a strong upward trend and minimal seasonal effects, supported by a calculated trend strength of 0.922 and seasonal strength of 0.05. Stationarity testing using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test confirmed that first differencing was necessary to stabilize the series. Several ARIMA models were fitted, with ARIMA(2,1,2) emerging as the best based on AIC and BIC values. When compared with the ETS(A, Ad, N) model, ARIMA(2,1,2) demonstrated superior forecasting performance with lower RMSE and MAE values. The findings suggest that the ARIMA model is more suitable for modeling and forecasting Nigeria's crude oil prices, offering a reliable tool for economic planning and risk management.

Keywords— Nigeria crude oil prices, ARIMA model, Time series analysis, ETS Modell, Stationarity test

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Crude oil continues to play a pivotal role in the global economy, serving as both a key driver of economic activity and a vital financial asset (Selvi et al., 2018). Its dual nature—as a physical commodity and a financial instrument—has made it the most extensively traded commodity worldwide, accounting for over 10% of global trade. Consequently, volatility in crude oil prices has far-reaching implications for global economic stability. Price increases often lead to

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inflationary pressures by raising transportation costs, which cascade into higher prices for food and other essential goods and services. In regions such as Europe and Africa, crude oil not only serves as a primary trade commodity but also functions as a benchmark for pricing other crude variants (Dunn et al., 2012; Ng'ang'a & Oleche, 2022).

Nigeria, Africa's largest oil producer and the sixth largest globally, is particularly susceptible to shifts in the global crude oil market. The nation's economy is heavily dependent on crude oil exports, making it highly vulnerable to price fluctuations. These fluctuations significantly influence macroeconomic indicators such as Gross Domestic Product (GDP), government revenue, fiscal balances, and trade performance (Oladosu, I. O., Ibeinmo, F. C., & Lasisi, O. K., 2023). Furthermore, the oil sector is a major source of employment in Nigeria, both directly and indirectly. As a result, oil price volatility poses not only economic but also social challenges, affecting job security and living standards across the country.

Given the strategic importance of oil price stability for economic planning and risk mitigation, accurate forecasting models are essential. Forecasting crude oil prices provides valuable insights to policymakers, investors, and industry stakeholders, enabling more informed decision-making. Over the years, several analytical techniques have been developed to address the challenges associated with oil price prediction.

Among the most commonly employed models are the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) and Exponential Smoothing State Space (ETS) models. ARIMA models—often referred to as the Box-Jenkins methodology—are particularly effective for modeling and forecasting univariate linear time series data (Wiri & Tuaneh, 2019; Rodhan & Jaaz, 2022; Shambulingappa et al., 2020). These models incorporate autoregressive and moving average components and apply differencing to achieve stationarity, offering a solid framework for medium-term forecasting. Despite their popularity, ARIMA models face limitations when dealing with nonlinearity, structural breaks, and high-frequency volatility, all of which are common in crude oil price data.

On the other hand, ETS models decompose a time series into error, trend, and seasonal components, applying exponential smoothing to each. ETS models are particularly advantageous when the data exhibit strong seasonal or trend patterns and are known for their simplicity, transparency, and adaptability to different time series structures. While ETS does not explicitly model external shocks or structural changes, it often performs well in stable trend and seasonality environments.

This study aims to assess the comparative effectiveness of the ARIMA and ETS models in forecasting Nigerian crude oil prices. By evaluating these models against real historical price data, the research seeks to determine which model offers superior predictive accuracy and robustness in the context of Nigeria's volatile crude oil market. Ultimately, the findings are expected to contribute to more reliable economic forecasting and policy formulation in resource-dependent economies like Nigeria.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research Design

A time series research design was employed in this study to account for the temporal dynamics inherent in crude oil price movements. This design was particularly appropriate given the historical volatility and trend behavior of oil prices over time. Monthly crude oil price data, spanning from January 2009 to May 2024, was utilized as the primary dataset. The ARIMA and ETS models were both fitted to this historical data in order to evaluate their performance and suitability for forecasting future Nigerian crude oil prices. By leveraging a long-term, continuous time series, the study aimed to identify the model with the most reliable predictive capabilities based on past trends and fluctuations.

2.2 Data Description and Source

This study utilized monthly crude oil spot prices covering the period from January 2009 to May 2024. The dataset was obtained from the official website of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). These data represent consistent and authoritative records of crude oil price movements relevant to the Nigerian economy. The extensive time span ensures adequate representation of long-term trends, seasonal patterns, and structural changes, making it suitable for robust time series modeling and forecasting using the ARIMA and ETS approaches.

2.3 Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) Process

The Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model is an extension of the Autoregressive Moving Average (ARMA) framework, widely employed in time series analysis for understanding data patterns and forecasting future values. While the ARMA model is suitable for stationary time series, the ARIMA model is designed to handle non-stationary data by incorporating a differencing step. Stationarity, where the statistical properties of the series remain constant over time, is a critical assumption in time series modeling. When the original data series exhibits non-stationary behavior, differencing the series one or more times can help achieve stationarity. A general ARIMA model is denoted as $ARIMA(p, d, q)$, where p represents the order of the autoregressive component, d denotes the number of times the data has been differenced to attain stationarity, and q indicates the order of the moving average component. This combination of processes allows the ARIMA model to flexibly capture both trend and autocorrelation structures in time series data.

To determine the most appropriate ARIMA model for forecasting, analysts typically examine the Autocorrelation Function (ACF) and Partial Autocorrelation Function (PACF) plots. These diagnostic tools help identify the suitable lag orders for the autoregressive (AR) and moving average (MA) components of the model. The estimation of the ARIMA model is commonly carried out using the Box-Jenkins methodology, which involves a systematic approach of model identification, parameter estimation, and diagnostic checking (Zhao & Wang, 2014). This iterative process ensures that the selected model adequately captures the underlying structure of the time series and provides reliable forecasts.

$$y_t = I + \theta_1 y_{t-1} + \theta_2 y_{t-2} + \dots + \theta_p y_{t-p} + \varphi_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} + \varphi_2 \varepsilon_{t-2} + \dots + \varphi_p \varepsilon_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t$$

2.3.1 Autocorrelation

Autocorrelation, also known as serial correlation, refers to the degree of association between the current values of a time series and its past (lagged) values. In other words, it measures how observations in a time series relate to previous observations over successive time periods. Autocorrelation is a key concept in time series analysis, as it helps determine the presence of patterns, trends, or repetitive structures within the data. High autocorrelation suggests that past values have a strong influence on future values, which is critical in model selection and forecasting.

$$x_k = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{k=0}^{k=n} (y_t - \bar{y})(y_{t-k} - \bar{y})}{\sum_{k=0}^{k=n} (x_t - \bar{x})^2}}$$

for $k = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$

Where \bar{y} is the mean of the given time series, y_t is the series of observations at time

period t and y_{t-k} is a series of observations k lags apart.

2.3.2 Partial autocorrelation

Partial autocorrelation at lag k measures the direct relationship between a time series observation and its lagged value at k periods, after removing the effects of all intermediate lags between them. In essence, it isolates the influence of the lag- k observation from the indirect effects of other lags. This function is a fundamental tool in the Box-Jenkins methodology for time series modeling, as it helps determine the appropriate lag length for the autoregressive (AR) component of an ARIMA(p,d,q) model. By analyzing the partial autocorrelation function (PACF), one can identify how many past values should be included in the AR part of the model.

2.4 ETS MODEL

The ETS (Error, Trend, Seasonal) model is a forecasting approach that builds on the principles of exponential smoothing to model and predict time series data. It explicitly accounts for three core components that often characterize time-dependent data: the error term, the trend, and the seasonal variation. Each of these components can be modeled in different ways: additive, multiplicative, or none, depending on the nature of the data and how the underlying patterns behave over time.

The error component represents the random variability or noise in the data. The trend captures the long-term direction, which could be increasing, decreasing, or flat, and may also be damped to reflect a gradual slowing of the trend. Seasonality accounts for regular, repeating fluctuations over

fixed intervals, such as monthly or quarterly cycles. ETS models are particularly well suited for time series that exhibit clear trend and seasonal structures. They are valued for their interpretability and their ability to automatically identify the best-fitting model through the use of information criteria such as the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC).

2.4.1 ETS (A, A, A)

This is ETS model with Additive error, Additive trend and Additive seasonality with observation equation given as follows:

$$y_t = l_{t-1} + b_{t-1} + s_{t-m} + e_t$$

State equations are defined as follows

1. Level :

$$l_t = l_{t-1} + b_{t-1} + \alpha e_t$$

2. Trend:

$$b_t = b_{t-1} + \beta e_t$$

3. Seasonality:

$$s_t = s_{t-m} + \gamma e_t$$

where

l_t is the level

b_t is the trend

s_t is the seasonal component

m is the seasonality period

α, β, γ are the smoothing parameters

e_t is the white noise

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Nigeria Crude Oil Price 2009 - 2024

Statistic	Value
Minimum	14.28
First Quartile	58.45
Median	76.91
Mean	78.52
Third Quartile	104.62
Maximum	130.10
Variance	669.01
Standard Deviation	25.87

Table 1 provides the descriptive statistics for Nigeria’s crude oil prices from 2009 to 2024 indicate significant price variability over the period. Prices ranged from a minimum of \$14.28 to a maximum of \$130.10, with a mean of \$78.52 and a median of \$76.91, suggesting a fairly symmetric distribution. The interquartile range (from \$58.45 to \$104.62) shows considerable spread within the middle 50% of the data. The standard deviation of 25.87 and variance of 669.01 further reflect high volatility in crude oil prices during the study period.

Figure. 1: Time plot of Nigeria Crude Oil Price from January 2009 to May 2024

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Figure 1 displays the time series plot of Nigeria's crude oil prices spanning from January 2009 to May 2024. The graph illustrates significant fluctuations over the years, reflecting the inherent volatility of the global oil market.

In the early part of the period, there is a noticeable upward trend, with prices steadily increasing from 2009 through to around 2011. This is followed by a phase of high prices with intermittent spikes that persist until approximately 2014. A sharp decline is observed between 2014 and 2016, during which oil prices dropped below \$50 per barrel, likely due to a global supply glut and weakening demand.

From 2016 to 2019, oil prices experienced moderate recovery, although they remained below the highs recorded in the earlier years. A dramatic plunge occurred in early 2020, corresponding with the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, which severely disrupted global demand for oil. This was followed by a strong rebound in 2021, with prices reaching their peak during the entire study period.

In the most recent years, from 2022 to 2024, the prices have shown moderate fluctuations, suggesting a period of relative stabilization, albeit with continued sensitivity to global economic and geopolitical factors.

3.1 Trend strength and Seasonal Strength

The Trend and Seasonal for the Nigeria crude oil price were obtained as follows

$$F_T = \max\left(0, 1 - \frac{\text{Var}(R_t)}{\text{Var}(T_t - R_t)}\right)$$

$$F_S = \max\left(0, 1 - \frac{\text{Var}(R_t)}{\text{Var}(S_t - R_t)}\right)$$

Where

T_t is the trend component

S_t is the seasonal component

R_t is the remainder (residual) component

Table 2: Trend and Seasonal Strength result

Trend Strength	Seasonal Strength
0.922	0.05

Table 2 provides the analysis trend and seasonal strengths of the Nigeria crude oil price time series, which reveals that the data is predominantly influenced by a strong trend component, with a calculated trend strength of 0.922. This indicates a clear and consistent directional movement in crude oil prices over time. In contrast, the seasonal strength is notably low, at 0.05, suggesting that seasonal patterns have a minimal effect on the price fluctuations. Overall, the results imply that while crude oil prices in Nigeria exhibit significant long-term trends, they are not strongly affected by recurring seasonal variations.

Figure. 2: Seasonal Box plot

The seasonal box plot in Fig.2 illustrates the distribution of crude oil prices across different time periods, representing the twelve months of the year. Each box reflects the spread of prices within each period, showing the median, interquartile range, and the overall variability of prices. While there is some fluctuation in price distribution from one period to another, the differences are not pronounced, suggesting that there is no strong or consistent seasonal pattern in the data. The plot reveals that crude oil prices have experienced substantial variability across all periods, with wide interquartile ranges and extended whiskers indicating considerable volatility. The medians across the months remain relatively stable, and there are no distinct patterns of peaks or troughs that would indicate a recurring seasonal effect. This visual evidence supports the earlier conclusion

that seasonality has a minimal impact on crude oil prices, with long-term trends and external market forces playing a more dominant role in shaping price movements.

Trained data

Trained data

Figure 4: PACF Plot of the raw data

Table 3: Dickey-Fuller test for Stationarity

Series	Dickey-Fuller	Lag order	p-value	Remark
Initial series	-2.1582	5	0.5102	Non stationary
First differenced series	-5.5132	5	0.01	Stationary

The Dickey-Fuller test results In Table 3 indicate that the initial crude oil price series is non-stationary, with a test statistic of -2.1582 and a p-value of 0.5102. However, after applying first differencing, the series becomes stationary, as evidenced by a significantly lower test statistic of -5.5132 and a p-value of 0.01. This suggests that differencing is required to stabilize the mean of the series before modeling.

Trained data

Figure 5: ACF Plot of the differenced data

Trained data

Figure 6: PACF Plot of the differenced data

Table 4: ARIMA Model for Nigeria crude oil prices

Model	AIC	BIC
ARIMA (2, 1, 2)	1154.11	1169.85
ARIMA (0, 1, 1)	1154.62	1160.93
ARIMA (1, 1, 0)	1155.14	1161.43
ARIMA (0, 1, 3)	1156.32	1168.91
ARIMA (2, 1, 3)	1156.11	1175.00

3.2 ARIMA Model selection

The ARIMA model comparison for Nigeria's crude oil prices in Table 4 shows that the ARIMA (2,1,2) model has the lowest AIC (1154.11) and BIC (1169.85) values among the models tested. This suggests that ARIMA(2,1,2) provides the best fit to the data based on these information criteria, indicating it is the most suitable model for forecasting crude oil prices.

Figure 7: Residuals plot from ARIMA(2, 1, 2)

Table 5: ARIMA (2, 1, 2) and ETS (A, Ad, N) Model for Nigeria crude oil prices

Model	AIC	BIC	AICC	RMSE	MAE
ARIMA (2, 1, 2)	1154.11	1169.85	1154.48	6.7086	5.0536
ETS(A, Ad, N)	1571.78	1590.71	1572.29	6.8992	5.1302

3.3 ARIMA and ETS Model

The comparison between the ARIMA(2,1,2) model and the ETS(A, Ad, N) model for forecasting Nigeria’s crude oil prices indicates that the ARIMA model performs better. It has lower values for AIC (1154.11), BIC (1169.85), AICC (1154.48), RMSE (6.7086), and MAE (5.0536) compared to the ETS model. These results suggest that ARIMA(2,1,2) offers greater accuracy and a better fit for the data than the ETS model.

Figure 8: Residuals plot from ETS(A,A,N)

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Figure 9: ARIMA Model forecasting 2023 - 2024

Figure 10: ETS Model forecasting 2023 - 2024

4.0 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study employed a time series approach to assess and compare the forecasting capabilities of ARIMA and ETS models using monthly crude oil prices from January 2009 to May 2024. The historical data, sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria, revealed significant volatility and a pronounced trend component, while seasonal effects were minimal. The stationarity analysis using the Dickey-Fuller test confirmed the need for differencing to stabilize the series, a prerequisite for accurate time series modeling. Descriptive and visual analyses further illustrated the dynamic nature of oil price movements, driven largely by macroeconomic and geopolitical factors. The observed fluctuations, including major declines and recoveries, underscored the importance of selecting a robust forecasting model for reliable economic planning.

Among the models evaluated, the ARIMA(2,1,2) model emerged as the most suitable for forecasting Nigeria's crude oil prices. It outperformed the ETS(A, Ad, N) model across multiple evaluation metrics, including AIC, BIC, RMSE, and MAE, indicating superior model fit and predictive accuracy. This finding highlights the strength of the ARIMA framework in capturing the linear components and structural dynamics of oil price time series. Consequently, the ARIMA

model provides a valuable tool for policymakers, analysts, and investors seeking to anticipate future oil price trends and make informed economic decisions in a highly volatile market environment.

REFERENCES

Ahmed, A., & Shabri, A. B. (2014). Forecasting crude oil price using multilayer feedforward neural network. *Journal of Physical Science*, 25(1), 49–63.

Dunn, D., Mutti, J., & Vigfusson, R. (2012). *Global oil markets and the U.S. economy: Some rules of thumb*. Board of Governors of the Federal Reserve System.

Mensah, J. O. (2015). Crude oil price forecasting using support vector machine. *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 116(23), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.5120/20408-2935>

Mombeini, H., & Yazdani-Chamzini, A. (2014). Modeling oil price uncertainty: A hybrid artificial neural network and GARCH approach. *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, 4(3), 373–381.

Ng'ang'a, S. I., & Oleche, M. (2022). Forecasting crude oil prices using GARCH-type models: Evidence from Brent and WTI. *Journal of Economics and Financial Analysis*, 6(1), 25–41.

Oladosu, I. O., Ibeinmo, F. C., & Lasisi, O. K. (2023). The impact of crude oil price volatility on Nigeria's economy. *African Journal of Economic Policy*, 30(2), 118–135.

Rodhan, A. A., & Jaaz, H. M. (2022). Forecasting crude oil prices using ARIMA models. *Energy Economics Letters*, 9(1), 1–8.

Selvi, M., Nasir, M. A., & Yilmaz, A. (2018). Oil prices and economic activity: Evidence from the G7 countries. *Energy Sources, Part B: Economics, Planning, and Policy*, 13(1), 1–7.

Shambulingappa, N., Rajesh, R., & Kumar, N. (2020). ARIMA model for crude oil price forecasting: A case study. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, 9(2), 1351–1355.

Wiri, R. M., & Tuaneh, B. A. (2019). Forecasting Nigerian crude oil price using ARIMA model. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Multidisciplinary Studies*, 5(6), 24–30.

Zhao, L., & Wang, S. (2014). *Research on forecasting model of crude oil price based on improved ARIMA model*. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 5(9), 121–128.